

Conditional Score-based Diffusion Models for Lung CT Scans Generation

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Abstract—Chest CT scans are essential in diagnosing lung abnormalities, including lung cancer, but their utility in training deep learning models is often pushed back by limited data availability, high labeling costs, and privacy concerns. To address these challenges, this study explores the use of score-based diffusion models for the conditional generation of lung CT scans slices. Two generation scenarios are explored: one limited to lung segmentation masks and another incorporating both lung and nodule segmentation mappings to guide the synthesis process. The proposed methods are custom U-Net architecture models trained to predict the scores in Variance Preserving (VP) and Variance Exploding (VE) Stochastic Differential Equations (SDEs), composing the primary ground for comparison in conditional sample generation. The results demonstrate the VP SDEs model’s superiority in generating high-fidelity images, as evidenced by high SSIM (0.894) and PSNR (28.6) values, as well as low domain-specific FID (173.4), MMD (0.0133) and ECS (0.78) scores. The generated images consistently followed the conditional mapping guidance during the generation process, effectively producing realistic lung and nodule structures, highlighting their potential for data augmentation in medical imaging tasks. While the models achieved notable success in generating accurate 2D lung CT scan slices given simple conditional image region mappings, future work surrounds the extension of these methods to 3D conditional generation and the use of richer conditional mappings to account for broader anatomical variations. Nevertheless, this study holds promise for improvement in computer-aided systems through the support in deep learning model training for lung disease diagnosis and classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chest Computer Tomography (CT) scans are crucial in medical imaging for diagnosing and evaluating chest abnormalities. They provide detailed images of anatomical structures, and they particularly play a key role in identifying lung disorders and lung cancer, one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths [1]. While advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly Deep Learning, have aided Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems in lung nodules detection and classification [2, 3, 4], they face great challenges due to limitations of data availability for model training [5].

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Creating such data collections is challenging due to high costs, time requirements, and the need for medical experts to correctly label and identify data points [6], ensuring that DL models are trained with correct and medical-trustworthy data. Additionally, privacy concerns and strict data protection regulations are also heavy factors to the lack of available data. Consequently, data augmentation offers a practical solution to overcome these limitations by generating diverse data points from the original ones to improve the generalization of DL models. In image data augmentation, it is common to use rotations, translations, and cropping to expand datasets. However, in the medical setting, it does not make sense to apply some of these techniques, as there must be spatial-anatomical correctness in the images.

To fight this issue, Image Generative AI models have emerged as a promising alternative [6, 7], enabling the creation of synthetic data that has realistic structural and anatomical properties from the original data it was trained on, allowing the enhancement and augmentation of real datasets with greater diversity. In the past few years, various Image Generative AI algorithms have been applied to the medical imagery scene, namely Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and Diffusion Models (DMs). VAEs offer the simplest models to train, but produce the blurriest and less defined samples out of the three types [8]. GANs were for a long the state-of-the-art models for image generation, despite their very unstable training process [9]. Given its predominant use and sharp results, many GAN variations have been proposed to be applied in the context of medical imaging, mainly in style-transfer tasks and in-painting tasks [10, 11]. DMs [12] are heavier and generally more complex models that generate images by starting with random noise and iteratively refining it to produce a coherent image. However, in recent times, they have surpassed GANs in terms of image sampling fidelity and quality [13].

This paper utilizes Score-based DMs [14] to generate lung CT scan slices, focusing exclusively on the lung area, under two conditional generation scenarios. The first scenario constrains the model to generate lung anatomical content within a binary mask, which specifies the regions corresponding to the lung area. The second scenario introduces an additional layer of complexity by conditioning the model on both the lung area and a nodule segmentation area, guiding the generation of a nodule-like structure within the specified region.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II delves into the definition and learning process of

Score-based DMs and conditional generation. Next, Section III presents the dataset used for the following experiments, the model architecture employed, and training details and settings, while Section IV discusses the results obtained from the work conducted and some limitations. Lastly, Section V sums up the experiments performed and their results, and presents future considerations for this line of work.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Score-based Diffusion Models

It is possible to define a continuous diffusion process $\{\mathbf{x}(t)\}_{t=0}^T$ with $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$, for an image of dimensions $H \times W$, where $t \in [0, T]$ resembles the time variable of the process. Let p_0 be the original data distribution such that $\mathbf{x}(0) \sim p_0$ is an i.i.d. sample of the dataset, and p_T a prior distribution that allows for tractable extraction of samples, for example a Gaussian distribution, such that $\mathbf{x}(T) \sim p_T$. Then, the stochastic process can be constructed as the solution to the following Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE)

$$d\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t)dt + g(t)d\mathbf{w}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the standard Wiener process, $\mathbf{f}(\cdot, t)$ is a vector-valued function named the *drift* coefficient of $\mathbf{x}(t)$, and $g(t)$ is a scalar function known as the *diffusion* coefficient of $\mathbf{x}(t)$ [14].

The \mathbf{f} and g functions in (1) can be defined to compose different SDEs. In particular, when using

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{1}{2}\beta(t)\mathbf{x}, \quad g(t) = \sqrt{\beta(t)}, \quad (2)$$

one achieves a Variance Preserving (VP) SDE [14] that yields a process with fixed variance, where $\beta(t)$ is a monotonically increasing function of noise scale.

In contrast, Variance Exploding (VE) SDEs [14] use diffusion signals with large variance that typically explodes as $t \rightarrow \infty$, and define the *drift* and *diffusion* coefficients as

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{0}, \quad g(t) = \sqrt{\frac{d[\sigma^2(t)]}{dt}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma^2(t)$ is also a monotonically increasing function.

By sampling $\mathbf{x}(T) \sim p_T$ and reversing the process of (1) it is possible to obtain samples $\mathbf{x}(0) \sim p_0$. The reverse diffusion process can be constructed with another stochastic [14] process defined by the reverse-time SDE

$$d\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) - g^2(t)\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x})]dt + g(t)d\bar{\mathbf{w}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{w}}$ is a standard Wiener process when time flows backwards from T to 0, and dt is an infinitesimal negative timestep. The forward SDE and reverse SDE can be interpreted as in Fig. 1, where the forward process iteratively adds noise to the data until it resembles a data point from the prior distribution p_T , while the reverse process denoises a noise sample until it generates a realistic sample similar to those from the original distribution p_0 .

Note that if the score function of each marginal distribution, $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x})$, is known for all t , then it is possible to

Fig. 1. Representation of the forward and reverse diffusion processes.

simulate the reverse process from (4) to sample from p_0 . In order to estimate the score, a time-informed score-based neural network s_θ can be optimized such that $s_\theta(\mathbf{x}(t), t) \simeq \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x})$. Given that the true score $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x})$ is not known, denoising score matching [15] can be used to replace the true score with $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_{0t}(\mathbf{x}(t)|\mathbf{x}(0))$. The optimization of the model's parameters θ is formulated by

$$\theta^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_t \left\{ \lambda(t) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}(0)} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}(t)|\mathbf{x}(0)} \left[\left\| s_\theta(\mathbf{x}(t), t) - \nabla_{\mathbf{x}(t)} \log p_{0t}(\mathbf{x}(t)|\mathbf{x}(0)) \right\|_2^2 \right] \right\}, \quad (5)$$

with λ being an appropriate positive weighting function [16], t uniformly sampled over $[0, T]$, $\mathbf{x}(0) \sim p_0$ and $\mathbf{x}(t) \sim p_{0t}(\mathbf{x}(t)|\mathbf{x}(0))$. The optimized score-based model s_{θ^*} can then be used to substitute $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x})$ by $s_{\theta^*}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)$ in (4).

Lastly, the SDE in (4) can be solved with numerical methods. In particular, this work uses a predictor-corrector algorithm [14] that, at each timestep, first predicts an estimate of the sample at the next step with the Euler-Maruyama method, and then has its marginal distribution corrected through Langevin MCMC [17].

B. Conditional Generation

The framework presented in II-A not only allows to generate data from p_0 , but also from $p_0(\mathbf{x}(0)|\mathbf{y})$ [14], where \mathbf{y} dictates the generation condition. Considering a forward SDE such as in (1), solving the following reverse-time SDE allows for sampling from $p_t(\mathbf{x}(t)|\mathbf{y})$ by starting from $p_T(\mathbf{x}(T)|\mathbf{y})$:

$$d\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) - g(t)^2 \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y})]dt + g(t)d\bar{\mathbf{w}}. \quad (6)$$

Similarly, a time-dependent score-predicting neural network s_θ that receives the condition \mathbf{y} as input can be optimized to perform the estimation of $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y})$, substituting the term on (6) by $s_{\theta^*}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{y}, t)$.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset

The dataset used in this study was constructed from the publicly available Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC) dataset [18], [19], its nodule annotations, and a collection of lung segmentation masks of LIDC's data obtained through the application of the segmentation model of [20]. The LIDC dataset consists of 1,018 thoracic CT scans for lung cancer screening, with each case annotated by four radiologists to classify masses into three categories: non-nodule lesions

Fig. 2. Example of lung-restricted CT scan slice (left) and corresponding image content mapping (right). This pair of images denotes a data point in the dataset of this study as the image to be generated and the conditional generation mapping, respectively.

$\geq 3mm$, nodules $\geq 3mm$, and nodules $< 3mm$. The CT scans are represented as 3D volumes with dimensions $N \times 512 \times 512$, where N resembles the number of slices in the scan. In this work, 80% of the scans are used for training, while the remaining are left for testing, ensuring that no CT scan slice in the training set will be seen in the testing set. Furthermore, for each CT scan, only the slices between indices 30 and 90 are considered to compose this work’s dataset. The database used in the experiments of this work ensures, on the corresponding cited description paper, that the necessary ethical approvals regarding data access were obtained.

Afterwards, the lung segmentation masks and nodule annotations were used to generate content mappings for each slice in the CT scans. These mappings label the region outside the lung area as 0, the regions within the lung area as 1, and the regions within nodules as 2. Each nodule annotation is formed by the 50% consensus of all annotations for the given nodule, meaning that a voxel will belong to the final annotation mask if it is present in at least half of the available annotations.

Considering that the focus of this study is to generate lung content based on specific area mappings, two tasks were designed to achieve this goal. The first task uses only the lung segmentation masks as conditional mappings, resulting in a dataset containing around 50,000 lung area mappings and their corresponding CT slices. The second task incorporates both lung and nodule segmentation masks, producing a smaller dataset of approximately 4,000 mappings and their associated CT slices. Furthermore, this study also focuses on only synthesizing content within the lung, so, each slice’s content is restricted to the lung area using the aforementioned lung segmentation masks, and each slice is then converted to a $[0, 1]$ value range with min-max normalization, as part of preprocessing.

Fig. 2 illustrates an example of a data point of the second task dataset: a lung CT scan slice, restricted to the lung region, and its corresponding lung area and nodule area content mapping.

Fig. 3. U-Net architecture of the score-based diffusion model.

B. Model Architecture

The model architecture used in this study is a custom U-Net with seven encoder stages, a bottleneck stage, and seven decoder stages, as shown in Fig. 3. All encoder, bottleneck, and decoder stages consists of two ResNet blocks, followed by linear attention and normalization with residual connections. The blocks are structured similarly, except in the final stage, where encoder blocks perform downsampling, while decoder blocks do upsampling, and each encoder block output is concatenated to the input of the respective decoder block by the channel dimension. All convolutions inside the model have kernels of size 3, stride 1, and padding 1, and normalization is performed through Group Normalization with 4 groups. Note that the input for this network corresponds to the concatenation of a noised lung-restricted CT image, $x(t)$, and the generative-guiding conditional mapping y , as pictured in Fig. 3.

Timestep information is encoded using a positional embedding based on sine and cosine functions. This embedding is further processed by a shallow multi-layer perceptron (MLP), consisting of a fully connected layer, a GELU activation, and another fully connected layer. The resulting embedding is added to the ResNet blocks at each U-Net stage during the forward pass. Fig. 4 illustrates the overall structure of the ResNet blocks along side the timestep embedding MLP.

Additionally, an autoencoder model with a similar architecture to the score-based model was defined, without the timestep embeddings and skip connections. This model allows to compute image generation test metrics further in the work, by using the images latent representation as feature

Fig. 4. Time Embedding MLP and ResNet Block architectures used in the score-based diffusion model.

embeddings.

C. Training Details

Two models were trained for both the VP SDE and VE SDE diffusion processes, with $t \in [0, 1]$. The $\beta(t)$ function in the VP SDE was defined as $\beta(t) = 0.1 + 19.9t$, while the $\sigma(t)$ function for the VE SDE was defined as $\sigma(t) = 0.01 \times 100^t$.

The training process of these models is divided into two stages. Firstly, the models are solely trained on data that has no nodule conditional mapping. Therefore, the models will be initially focused on learning to synthesize realistic lung content concerning the lung area given in the conditional mapping. The models are trained for 20 epochs with batch size 10, learning rate 5×10^{-5} , and L_2 regularization weight decay of 1×10^{-12} , using the AdamW optimizer. These hyperparameters were selected based on empirical experimentation, where different values were evaluated across multiple training runs to optimize model performance. After the first stage, the resulting models are used as pre-trained bases, and they begin training on data with nodule conditional mapping information to learn to generate nodule-like content within the specified nodule mapping area. This second stage is trained for 40 epochs, with the remaining training settings equal to the first stage's. The whole training pipeline is exemplified in Fig. 5.

Exponential Moving Average (EMA) is also an important mechanism used to update the model's parameters during training, maintaining a smoothed version of the model parameters over time and improving model generalization. More specifically, it is computed through the weighted average between the current model parameters θ_t and its previous EMA parameters $\theta_{t-1}^{\text{EMA}}$, as described in (7). The weight factor α was set to 0.999 during the training of all models, and the final version of the EMA parameters are employed for model testing.

$$\theta_t^{\text{EMA}} = \alpha \theta_{t-1}^{\text{EMA}} + (1 - \alpha) \theta_t \quad (7)$$

The autoencoder model was trained on the same lung image data as the score-based model, for 200 epochs, batch size 32 and learning rate 2×10^{-4} , using the Adam optimizer with beta values $\beta_1 = 0.5$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$.

D. Performance Evaluation

1) *Evaluation Setup*: In order to obtain the evaluation metrics values, 100 images are sampled from each model by solving the reverse-time SDE of a diffusion process with

Fig. 5. Training stages of the models for both lung CT scan slices conditional generation tasks.

1000 timesteps. At each timestep, one Euler-Maruyama predictor step is performed, followed by two Langevin corrector steps. After 5 rounds, the average evaluation results are computed.

2) *Pixel-level Metrics*: Image generation is often evaluated using pixel-wise metrics that usually measure structural and pixel-level accuracy, or textural components of some given real and generated sets of images. In particular, this work uses pixel-level metrics such as Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM).

PSNR measures the fidelity of reconstructed images compared to their references, reflecting how closely the pixel intensities match, always yielding a positive value such that the higher the ratio is, the more similar the generated image is to the reference, indicating better reconstruction quality and lower distortion. On the other hand, SSIM focuses on structural and perceptual differences, evaluating luminance, contrast, and texture across the image, outputting a value between -1 and 1, where greater positive values indicate greater structural similarity and perceptual quality.

3) *Distributional Metrics*: Although pixel-wise metrics are useful for assessing local fidelity, they may not capture the overall quality or diversity of the synthetic images. Hence, distributional metrics are also commonly used to compare feature-level statistics between sets of real and generated images to quantify the realism and diversity of synthetic images. This work employs distributional metrics such as Fréchet Inception Distance (FID), Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD), and Embedded Characteristic Score (ECS).

FID computes the similarity between distributions of real and generated images by comparing their feature representations extracted from the a pre-trained neural network, traditionally Inception-v3 [21], using the means and covariances of the features, with lower FID values pointing to high-level feature similarity and close alignment between the distributions. Next, MMD evaluates the divergence between two distributions by comparing their mean embeddings in a reproducing kernel Hilbert space, such that, the smaller the MMD measure, the more similar the generated and real datasets are. Lastly, ECS is a recent distributional metric [22] that is also computed using features from the original and generated datasets, except that it does not leverage the normality assumption, such as FID, taking more into consideration the distribution tail behavior. Moreover, ECS is parameterized by a variable T that controls the sensitivity of the metrics.

While it is common to use the pre-trained Inception-v3 network to obtain feature embeddings from either distributions to compute the aforementioned metrics, the network was trained on the ImageNet database, and, therefore, it was not exposed to medical imagery during training. Hence, the encoder of the previously mentioned autoencoder model is used to transform the real and generated images into latent feature vectors, allowing for the computation of the test metrics with domain-specific model embeddings.

Fig. 6. Three examples of samples generated with only lung area conditioning (one per row), with the original image, conditional generation mapping, VP SDE score-based model sample and VE SDE score-based model sample, by column order from left to right.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Lung-only Conditional Generation

As previously mentioned, this generation task focused on producing realistic lung content from lung CT scan slices, given the lung area as a conditional generation mapping to the model, excluding any nodule-specific information. Fig. 6 displays some test lung CT slices, along side their respective lung area conditional mapping, and resulting model outputs. It is noted that all presented samples follow strictly the conditional mapping areas, without any kind of mask being applied to the samples.

Table I presents the average results for pixel-wise metrics, including SSIM scores computed for the entire 512×512 images and for center-cropped regions of size 256×256 , as well as average PSNR scores. The evaluation of SSIM on the cropped images minimizes the influence of the null background, enabling a more accurate assessment of image quality.

The SSIM results demonstrate good structural similarity between the VP SDE score-based model samples and the original test images, with average scores of 0.894 for the full image and 0.725 for the cropped regions. In contrast, the VE SDE model produced lower SSIM values of 0.788 and 0.625 for the full and cropped images, respectively, indicating inferior structural fidelity. This observation is further supported by the first row of sample images in Fig. 6, where the VE SDE score-based model struggled to generate lung content, while the VP SDE model successfully produced content.

Additionally, the VP SDE model achieved a higher PSNR score compared to the VE SDE model ($28.6 > 27.2$), pointing to superior pixel-level fidelity relative to the original test images. Together, these results highlight the VP SDE model’s ability to produce higher-quality reconstructions

TABLE I

PIXEL-LEVEL METRICS (SSIM AND PSNR) FOR LUNG-ONLY CONDITIONAL GENERATION.

SDE	SSIM ₅₁₂ ↑	SSIM ₂₅₆ ↑	PSNR ↑
VP	0.894	0.725	28.6
VE	0.788	0.625	27.2

TABLE II

DISTRIBUTION METRICS (FID, MMD AND ECS) FOR LUNG-ONLY CONDITIONAL GENERATION.

SDE	FID ↓	MMD ↓	ECS _{T=1.0} ↓	ECS _{T=0.5} ↓
VP	214.3	0.0135	1.80	0.94
VE	314.0	0.0152	5.01	2.71

both in terms of structural similarity and pixel-level accuracy.

Next, Table II presents the results for distributional metrics, FID, MMD, and ECS, assessing the overall quality and diversity of the generated samples using the autoencoder’s latent representations as feature embeddings.

The results reinforce the findings from the pixel-wise analysis, further demonstrating the superiority of the VP SDE model over the VE SDE model. Specifically, the VP SDE model achieves a significantly lower FID score ($214.3 > 314.0$), indicating closer alignment between the distributions of generated and real images. Similarly, the MMD results show a smaller discrepancy between the VP SDE samples and the original test images compared to the VE SDE samples ($0.0135 > 0.0152$), suggesting better feature-level similarity.

Moreover, the ECS metric provides additional information into the alignment of the distributions, particularly concerning their tails. Although most ECS values exceed 1, which indicates some deviation from distributional matching, the VP SDE model outperforms the VE SDE model again. This trend is observed for both parameter settings, $T = 1.0$ and $T = 0.5$, where the VP SDE model demonstrates a better match with the real data distribution, including its tail behavior.

In essence, the results collectively support the VP SDE score-based model’s superior capability to generate high fidelity and diverse samples, solely given the lung area mapping as the generation’s condition.

B. Lung and Nodule Conditional Generation

This second generation task focused on synthesizing lung content given not only the lung area mapping but also additional mapping information regarding the localization of nodule-like content. Fig. 7 presents some samples obtained through the VP and VE SDE score-based models that were trained with nodule-informed conditional mappings on top of the first task’s models. It is highlighted again how all samples respect the lung area boundaries present in the conditional mapping without any kind of post-processing.

As this task primarily focuses on generating realistic nodule content, alongside the surrounding lung structures, the SSIM metrics in Table III were calculated using 128×128

Fig. 7. Three examples of samples generated with lung area and nodule area conditioning (one per row), with the original image, conditional generation mapping, VP SDE score-based model sample and VE SDE score-based model sample, by column order from left to right.

TABLE III
PIXEL-LEVEL METRICS (SSIM AND PSNR) FOR LUNG AND NODULE
CONDITIONAL GENERATION.

SDE	SSIM ₁₂₈ ↑	SSIM ₆₄ ↑	PSNR ↑
VP	0.891	0.721	28.4
VE	0.768	0.620	26.8

and 64×64 cropped regions centered on each nodule area, as identified in the images’ conditional mappings. This approach provides a more targeted evaluation of the pixel-level fidelity of the generated nodule content relative to the original images.

The results demonstrate that the VP SDE model achieved SSIM scores of 0.891 and 0.721 for the 128-pixel and 64-pixel nodule-centered crops, respectively, indicating significantly better structural similarity to the reference images compared to the VE SDE model, which obtained lower SSIM scores of 0.768 and 0.620. For overall pixel-level quality across the entire 512×512 images, the PSNR metric further supports the VP model’s better performance, with a higher score of 28.4 compared to 26.8 for the VE model. This difference in performance is also visually evident in Fig. 7, particularly in the last row, where the VE model failed to synthesize any nodule-like content despite the presence of nodule information in the conditional mapping, whilst the VP model successfully generated realistic nodule structures.

Following, distributional metrics are also computed to address the fidelity and diversity of the generated images for this task compared to their original counterparts. Table IV presents the values for FID, MMD, and ECS, based on 100 generated samples and their corresponding reference image collections, as previously mentioned.

Despite the difference in conditional generation objective, additional training resulted in significant improvements in FID scores for both models compared to the results in Table

TABLE IV
DISTRIBUTION METRICS (FID, MMD AND ECS) FOR LUNG AND
NODULE CONDITIONAL GENERATION.

SDE	FID ↓	MMD ↓	ECS _{T=1.0} ↓	ECS _{T=0.5} ↓
VP	173.4	0.0133	1.52	0.78
VE	246.1	0.0137	4.89	2.75

II. The VP SDE model achieved a lower FID score of 173.4, outperforming the VE SDE model, which scored 246.1. This superior performance is further supported by the smaller MMD value of the VP model ($0.0133 < 0.0137$), consistent with the pixel-level metrics and previous generation task results.

Additionally, ECS values mostly decreased after further training, reflecting improvements in matching the distributional tails of the original dataset. The VP SDE model achieved ECS scores of 1.52 and 0.78 for $T = 1.0$ and $T = 0.5$, respectively, which are substantially lower than the corresponding values for the VE SDE model (4.89 for $T = 1.0$ and 2.75 for $T = 0.5$). These results reinforce the VP model’s ability to align more closely with the original data distribution, including its tails. Interestingly, while the VP model demonstrated consistent reductions in ECS scores for both T values, the VE model exhibited an increase in ECS for $T = 0.5$, despite the additional training.

C. Limitations

Although this work demonstrated promising results in using score-based diffusion models to generate realistic lung CT scans given some conditional generation mapping, some limitations should be addressed.

Firstly, the generated images are restricted to 2D slices, which do not account for the volumetric spatial consistency needed for full 3D CT scan synthesis. This limitation is particularly significant for clinical applications, as radiologists typically analyze CT data in a volumetric context. However, directly translating the networks for full 3D generation capability would imply a large increase in compute power and memory, posing a significant practical barrier.

Another limitation lies in the simplified conditional mappings used in this work. While the lung area and nodule segmentation masks provide a simple and direct process for guiding the generation process, they do not transmit any other anatomical structures or pathological variations that may be present in real scenarios. Expanding the conditioning criteria to include other comprehensive contextual information could improve the realism and applicability of the generated samples.

Furthermore, while the generated images display good structural similarity, pixel-level fidelity, and distributional metrics values, it remains uncertain whether or not these samples have enough quality to enhance the training of other models for computer vision tasks on lung CT scans. Despite the results suggesting potential for data augmentation, it is necessary to conduct further experiments to evaluate whether incorporating these synthetic images into training leads to

noticeable improvements in model performance.

Lastly, it is important to recognize that synthetic samples can inherit—and even amplify—biases present in the training data, such as the under-representation of specific nodule types or patient demographics. If left unaddressed, these biases may persist or become more pronounced in the generated data, leading to reduced fairness, degraded diagnostic performance, or the propagation of bias into downstream models relying on this data.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to implement and assess the potential of score-based diffusion models in generating high-fidelity lung CT scan slices under conditional settings with area mapping. Through the use of VP and VE SDEs, the produced score-based models were capable of synthesizing realistic lung anatomical structures, including nodule-like content, with good image and structural fidelity, while still proving realistic generation diversity. Across both pixel-level and distributional metrics, the VP SDE model consistently outperformed the VE SDE model, achieving high SSIM and PSNR scores, both in whole image and nodule-focused image regions, as well as lower FID, MMD and ECS values.

The results highlight the model's capability to generate images that accurately follow the guidance provided by the conditional mappings. This approach ensures that the synthesis process produces lung CT scans slices with realistic lung shapes, as the mappings are derived directly from real lung segmentation maps. Moreover, the VP SDE model demonstrated its effectiveness in generating nodule structures based on the specified conditional mappings, highlighting the potential of these generative models for applications such as data augmentation in deep learning tasks related to nodule detection and classification.

Future work should aim to extend the approach to 3D score-based diffusion models, enabling the synthesis of fully volumetric CT scans, while addressing the computational overhead introduced by the transition to cubic voxel data. Additionally, including more comprehensive conditional mappings, incorporating broader anatomical and pathological variations would be essential for enhancing the realism and utility of the generated samples. It will be also essential to quantify and mitigate any systematic biases in the future generated data before any synthetic data collection deployment for other diagnostic models training.

Finally, while the results suggest potential for data augmentation in training deep learning models for lung CT analysis, further validation is required to assess whether these synthetic images can significantly improve task performance. By addressing these challenges, this line of research holds immense promise for advancing medical image generation and enhancing CAD systems.

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